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Thought Leadership Paper

“Implementing Microsoft Teams in a company”

Year 2020 brought us the biggest challenge of the last years – we were encountered by the coronavirus disease, all continents were infected and the World Health Organization declared a public health emergency of international concern, the highest level of alarm under the international law. We were facing the pandemic. Governments around the globe announced restrictions in order to stop the virus from spreading. And restrictions had implications not only on our personal life but also on our working world, which I would like to address in the following paper.

Temporary limitations and restrictions were announced. Restrictions concerning movement (like limit of people allowed to commute together in public transport) or social distance (such as limit of people allowed to work together in one space, distance of 1,5 meters between workers and the restriction to wear mask while working) had implications on the working environment. Many companies decided that they close their offices and delegate employees to work remotely from their private facilities. And here is where the technology came into the light and played a vital role in the organization of the whole working world during the pandemic times.

An emerging technology that created opportunity for remote work was Microsoft Teams application, launched in 2017. This technology made it possible to stay connected despite the physical distance. Companies that rely on client contact may have been affected by the restrictions imposed by government during coronavirus pandemic. But video conferencing systems have become an asset to organizations as they enable to foster collaboration with client and maintain relationships with business partners from around the world. Video conferencing systems allow face-to-face interactions making virtual team members feel more engaged. The leading video conferencing platforms at the moment are Microsoft Teams and Zoom. Both platforms offer video conferencing capabilities, chat functionality and enable users to share and edit files in real time through a shared virtual workspace. Teams has the capacity of hosting up to 10,000 meeting participants which is why it is commonly chosen by big international corporations.

In the below paper I would like to share my thoughts about framework that would help to drive adoption of Microsoft Teams in an enterprise.

The service adoption framework starts with assembling your team, i.e. choosing change agents and champions, recruiting technical experts etc. Then define strategy and scenarios – align the business and technical needs. Assess organizational readiness including user groups, technical, governance, security. Build plan – prepare pilots, early adopter programs, champion readiness and scope of whole change across organization. And last but not least onboard employees, i.e. build awareness, onboarding and feedback into plan (include success stories).

Adoption Framework by Phase

Phase approach reduces complexity and manages issues around scope and scale. Enhancements based on customer implementations and feedback.

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When we want to implement a new tool, in our case Teams, we have to remember to drive adoption in the following knowledge areas: organizational development, business acumen, technical competence, marketing and communications, portfolio management, leadership capability.

1. Knowledge area: organizational development.

Remember that the change is for people, so concentrate your priorities and enthusiasm around people. Assessing knowledge of the majority of employees is a fundamental step to prepare a successful adoption plan. Another important thing is to listen to employee surveys and informal conversations because if we are the ones in charge of implementing new tool, i.e. Teams, in our organization then we are the bridge between company's strategy and day-to-day employee experience.

2. Knowledge area – business acumen

Service Adoption Specialists often have marketing background or IT background, but despite of the background, whoever drives the adoption needs to understand the strategic, competitive cultural, financial needs of his organization. Implementing virtual meetings on Teams instead of real face-to-face meetings is a huge culture alteration in a company. The five areas of business acumen are influencing company strategy and culture, methods of product improvements, service improvements, cost control, revenue increase.

3. Knowledge area – technical competence

It is a knowledge required to apply technology to business. Have in mind that technology costs goes beyond hardware and software. It is also cost of training, configuration and deployment time.

¹ Graphic from Microsoft course titled „Use the Microsoft service adoption framework to drive adoption in your enterprise“

4. Knowledge area – marketing and communications

In the context of service adoption, you have to communicate why, when, where, and how the change will occur in an appealing way. Some of those communication methods include email, posters, events, internal social networks, digital news. Using visual elements should help to retain information. Often employees resist change because no one has explained the change in terms that are meaningful to them.

5. Knowledge area – portfolio management

It is the ability to design and manage improvements into a cohesive employee experience roadmap. Roadmap should balance measurable business outcomes, technical capabilities and culture to deliver change gradually. Service Adoption Specialist should cooperate with IT department to create a right roadmap taking into account advices from stakeholders, executives and success owners.

6. Knowledge area – leadership

It is the ability to inspire others. Usually leader is the first one to talk at a meeting. In literature there is also a description of the “introvert leader”, a person who likes to review information ahead, reflect on it and during the meeting he is not shouting first for voice, but when he talks it is worth listening. In service adoption listening to others and analysis are the critical skills so such leader would surely suit in such role as well as an extrovert one.

In the first startup phase it is important to create team. Following roles are essential in the service adoption framework. First, executive sponsor, so a senior executive who cares about overall business outcomes. Second one is success owner so a person accountable for the success of this implementation, it is often a business leader and an IT service owner. Another one is project manager, so someone with day-to-day responsibilities for managing some projects, service adoption specialist mentioned before in this paper is a project manager. Then we have champions who provide individual support for employees during transition, they provide trainings and answer questions that colleagues may have during transition phase. Another key role relates to communications – someone has to help creating creative messages about this change (about introducing Teams tool) and design graphics. And the last one, technical expert with deep understanding of technical aspects, configuration and deployment of the new tool.

As mentioned earlier, we need to assess organizational readiness and in doing so a following change curve may help us. Change curve presented on the graphic below is universal, applies to all people in any situation.

Understanding the change curve

At the beginning there is usually a denial phase. People tend to deny that change needs to occur. They do not want to go out from their comfort zone and any change is going out of such zone. The solution for project manager is to inform people how this new change will benefit them. In case of Teams, adoption specialist could inform that during pandemic times remote work will not disrupt any ongoing project, team members can share video, chat and files all together.

Then there is resistance phase. It recommended to fight with it with such strategies as rewards for early adopters. Success stories are welcomed here, people will be less resistant when they know that their friend uses the new tool with success and is satisfied with it. Success story can be told by beginning with pointing out difficulties that someone had with the new tool and ending on positive outcome.

After hitting bottom at the diagram the curve goes up to exploration phase. People start to be more positive about the change, they start to explore new tool, it is about time to use champions. Barriers of entry or unreliable tool, problems with login to Teams, it all can push people back to resistance, so champions have a key role here to support others and help them with any questions they may have.

The last phase is called commitment. Employees are using the new tool on a regular basis but we have to be aware that it will last only as long as the new tool serves their needs. As soon as it will operate poorly, people will probably revert from it.

Having it all in mind, it is about time for step 2, that is experiment. The objective of this step is to initiate hands-on learning for prioritized business scenarios. Early experiments with champions on board are designed to build a self-educating community of champions who will later help all employees in the final transition. Creating a champions program is important part of the service adoption program because they provide peer-to-peer learning and feedback, and they provide enthusiasm to our change.

How to create a good champions program? Use the following checklist.

² Graphic from Microsoft course titled „Use the Microsoft service adoption framework to drive adoption in your enterprise“

First, search in entity's IT department or your social network in the company for enthusiastic champions. It is a good hint to also look for people who are engaged socially and speak freely about the upcoming change – both positively and negatively. If you recruit them they will help you implement the change instead of disrupting it.

Second. Build a Microsoft Team for the selected champions, so that they can share updates and their successes, they will start to build a community.

Third, equip them with materials that they will be able to give others.

Then, arrange regular meetings with champions and listen to their regular feedback, what is working and what needs to be amended.

Keep champions motivated, they play key role in implementing change in the organization, so they should be recognized and rewarded for their effort, for example they could receive privileged access to some company events.

Next point, communicate to all employees that there are champions ready to help them as the first contact. It is important to state clearly that champions are not IT help desk but they have a role of business representatives, they can explain how to use the new tool and when it may be helpful for a team, what features are worth recommending and using.

Step three of the adoption framework is to enable users. You are advised to prepare awareness campaign, collect and answer feedback. In practice it is also important to react on users' opinions and improve the tool.

Keys to adoption success

Research results below support suggested approach for building your adoption plan

Top reported activities for driving Office 365 adoption*

- ① Defined a vision and identified how Office 365 will be used
- ② Obtained proactive support from senior leadership to encourage use of Office 365
- ③ Provided training for end users
- ④ Raised awareness through email, Intranet announcements, posters, teaser videos, newsletters

% of respondents that rated activity as having above average importance

*Results of a Microsoft research study survey

³ Graphic from Microsoft course titled „Use the Microsoft service adoption framework to drive adoption in your enterprise“